

FAMILY SCROPHULARIACEAE JUSS. S. L. OF ALTAI MOUNTAIN COUNTRY

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Dataset on GBIF

Access to the dataset

Description

The dataset contains an updated list of representatives of the family Scrophulariaceae Juss. s. l. Altai mountain country (<http://altaiflora.asu.ru>). The data set is intended to provide all interested GBIF users with information about the distribution of the family within the AMC, determining the storage locations of material in world collections and other types of analyses (taxonomic, phenological, etc.) using available data sets in GBIF. For the first time for AMC, the system of the family Scrophulariaceae Juss. s. l. both its generic and species composition were published in the work of P. A. Kosachev (2010). According to this work, 13 genera and 82 species in the family Scrophulariaceae and 7 genera and 55 species in the family Pediculariaceae (Orobanchaceae Vent.) grow on the AMC territory.

Geographic scope

The database contains information on the distribution of the family Scrophulariaceae Juss. s. l. of the Altai Mountain Country (AMC) within the territories of Russia, Mongolia, China and Kazakhstan.

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